

SLEEP DISRUPTION MODELS

Sleep disorders are among the most frequent symptoms observed in Parkinson's disease (PD), with a prevalence of 60–70%. Sleep disruption can include hypersomnia, insomnia, rapid eye movement (REM) sleep behavior disorder (RBD), excessive daytime sleepiness (EDS), among others. Symptoms often appear in the early stages of the disease and progressively worsen during the course of PD, representing a major factor affecting the patient's quality of life. Below you will find a summary of PD animal models with reported sleep disruptions. Please note, this list is not comprehensive.

6-OHDA MODEL

- **Description:** 6-OHDA is a mitochondrial complex I and IV inhibitor that is administered through stereotaxic injection into the rat brain via the striatum, substantia nigra, or medial forebrain bundle (MFB). The route of administration affects pathology in this model – nigral or MFB injection will result in loss of nigral dopamine neurons followed by degeneration of striatal terminals within days, whereas striatal injection results in a progressive model that begins with degeneration of striatal dopamine terminals and results in loss of nigral dopamine neurons in a matter of weeks. Robust unilateral motor deficits are present and can appear in a manner of days or weeks, depending on the injected structure. Neuroinflammation, cognitive impairment, and GI dysfunction have also been reported in this model. aSyn pathology, however, is not present. Regarding sleep phenotypes, this model displays dysregulated circadian rhythms at the cardiovascular, activity, and gene/protein level and REM disturbances. These phenotypes, however, undergo partial recovery after a few weeks post-injection. In addition, injection site impacts phenotypes, with VTA injections causing sleep-wake disturbance and MFB lesions causing motor-related sleep alterations.
- **Recommended Use:** 6-OHDA is a potent inhibitor of mitochondrial respiration complexes I and IV. The robust degeneration and motor, cognitive, and GI dysfunction make this an attractive model. This model isn't preferred for studying the impact of aSyn-related interventions on behavioral phenotypes as aSyn pathology is absent in this model. Furthermore, the model is better suited to studying impact of nigrostriatal degeneration on sleep versus pathology in lower brain regions.
- **Helpful Resources:**
 - CRO Recommendations for the 6-OHDA Model - [Atuka](#), [Charles River Labs](#), [Psychogenics](#)

THY1 ASYN MASLIAH "LINE 61"

- **Description:** This transgenic mouse model overexpresses human wildtype *SNCA* under the Thy1 promoter. The model displays robust aSyn pathology, primarily in the cortex and limbic system. Loss of dopaminergic terminals in the striatum and inflammation occurs in this model at late timepoints. The line does not display loss of neurons in the substantia nigra. Regardless, motor symptoms are present in the model starting as early as 1 month of age. This model also displays impairments in GI function, sleep, cognition, and olfaction. Regarding sleep, this model displays dysregulated sleep-wake brain wave patterns and REM disturbance. Unpublished work has noted possible pathology in brain regions regulating sleep.
- **Recommended Use:** Pathology in this model is driven by aSyn overexpression (~1.5-3.5 fold). The model is recommended for researchers who want a transgenic mouse to study synuclein pathology or nonmotor/motor deficits driven by aSyn overexpression. This model is not ideal for looking at nigrostriatal degeneration. Molecular mechanisms of sleep dysfunction have yet to be uncovered but potentially linked to alpha-synuclein.
- **Helpful Resources:**

ICON KEY						
Model Properties			Pathology			
 Cognitive Impairments						

- Model information at [Alzforum](#) and [JPND](#)
- CRO Recommendations – [Psychogenics](#), [Scantox Neuro](#)
- Commercial Availability – this line is available at JAX (#038796)

ASYN PFF SLD MODEL

- **Description:** This model uses injection of recombinant aSyn amyloid that are 50nm or smaller (known as preformed fibrils or PFFs) into the mouse sublateral dorsal tegmental nucleus (SLD). Injection of these PFFs results in templating of the endogenous synuclein to induce pathological modifications. Injecting PFFs into the SLD results in RBD phenotypes of increased muscle activity during REM (no changes in REM sleep architecture) as early as one month post-injection. These behavioral changes are linked to increased aSyn pathology and SLD neuron loss. Furthermore, the model displays motor deficits caused by degeneration and aSyn pathology in the nigrostriatal system and GI dysfunction starting at 5 months post-injection.
- **Recommended Use:** Pathology in this model is driven by pathological changes in the endogenous aSyn protein. This model is recommended for researchers looking to observe aSyn pathology in multiple brain regions while avoiding aSyn overexpression. The model is not ideal for fast timelines for motor dysfunction.
- **Helpful Resources:**
 - Commercial aSyn PFF sources – [StressMarq aSyn PFFs](#).
 - CRO Recommendations (for striatal PFF model, not SLD PFF model) – [Atuka](#), [Psychogenics](#)
 - Review of PFF Model Phenotypes – Polinski, NK. (2021). *J Parkinsons Dis*, 11(4): 1555-1567.
 - Best Practices when Using aSyn PFFs – Polinski et al. (2018). *J Parkinsons Dis*, 8(2): 303-322.

MITOPARK MOUSE MODEL

- **Description:** The MitoPark model involves homozygous knockout of *Tfam* specifically in midbrain dopaminergic neurons, resulting in impairments in mtDNA maintenance and the mitochondrial respiratory chain. This model displays progressive loss of dopaminergic neurons in the nigra starting at 3 months, corresponding to a progressive loss of striatal dopamine neuron terminals. Motor deficits appear at 3 months of age and continue throughout the lifespan. Synuclein inclusions are observed in dopamine neurons beginning at 1.5 months. GI pathology and dysfunction are also prevalent in this line and appear prior to motor symptoms. Regarding sleep, studies have shown disruption of circadian rhythms (even elimination during prolonged light/dark) and sleep fragmentation.
- **Recommended Use:** This model is attractive in that presents with aSyn pathology, nigrostriatal degeneration, and motor dysfunction at early time points. It is important to note that the model does not necessarily reflect the pathogenic mechanisms of PD and may fail to recapitulate changes in other pathways that are important in disease. In addition, the mechanisms underlying sleep abnormalities in these mice remain unclear.
- **Helpful Resources:**
 - Summary of Line Phenotypes – [JPND Model Summary](#)
 - Commercial Availability – This model is not commercially available.

MCI-PARK MOUSE MODEL

- **Description:** The MCI-PARK model involves homozygous knockout of *Ndufs2* specifically in dopaminergic neurons, resulting in mitochondrial complex I inhibition in this model. Motor deficits are present in this model at early time points, starting with Levodopa-responsive phenotypes in the adhesive removal task at 30 days of age, open field test at 60 days of age, and gait abnormalities at 100 days of age. Dopamine neurochemistry deficits are present

ICON KEY						
Model Properties			Pathology			
Inducible	Constitutive Expression/Knockout	Nigrostriatal Degeneration	α-Synuclein Pathology	Inflammation	Motor Impairments	Cognitive Impairments

starting at 30 days of age and by 4-5 months of age approximately 40% of nigral dopamine neurons are lost. Sleep disturbances reported in this model start at 6 weeks and include significantly altered sleep-wake patterns, increased sleep fragmentation, and altered sleep-related brain wave activity. Sleep phenotypes continue and progress to late time-points in this model.

- **Recommended Use:** The model displays early, robust motor/non-motor phenotypes. However, degeneration in this model results from inhibition of mitochondrial complex I so the model does not necessarily reflect the PD pathogenic mechanisms and may fail to recapitulate changes in other pathways that are important in PD. The benefit of this model is that no neurotoxin injection is involved so safety concerns and injection artifacts are avoided.
- **Helpful Resources:**
 - Publication on Model Characterization – <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/34732887/>
 - Commercial Availability – This model is available at JAX (ID 036313).

ICON KEY						
Model Properties			Pathology			
 Cognitive Impairments						